

Experience Integrating an Interdisciplinary Schema of Project Based Learning on an Engineering Program

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Abstract

Interdisciplinary connections are featured as key booster in a Project Based Learning curriculum implementation (Yusri et al., 2024). Supported by significant teachers' guidance and appropriate resources which are considered primary components in the Gold Standard Design of a Project, multiple related areas can be integrated in project activities to enhance the learning process and develop skills. This document presents the experience of integrating the courses of Instrumentation and Measurements, Communication Systems, and Control Systems in a Project Based Learning schema for an Electronics Engineering Program. The experience was mainly guided for the Control Systems course. Extending curriculum elements and resources presented in (Ramírez-Scarpetta et al., 2024), multiple activities aimed at integrating these areas were proposed and performed with the students in two consecutive academic periods (2024-I, 2024-II). Opinions from students were collected to assess the relevance of the schema and the level of alignment with the main elements of the project design in a curriculum. The assessment results highlight engagement and motivation from students showing how meaningful this schema could be in an Engineering program.

Keywords: Control Systems; Curriculum Implementation; Engineering Education; Interdisciplinary Connections; Project Based Learning.

1 Introduction

Control Systems is a field that requires interdisciplinary work (Rossiter et al., 2023) such as communication, instrumentation, digital processing signals, and others. With applications to multiple engineering fields, the study of control systems requires students to engage with real-world problems and hands-on activities. An effective education strategy is crucial to support this learning process and Project Based Learning (PBL) has been widely adopted for this purpose. Additionally, the integrative project strategy is being considered alongside PBL to further enhance the learning experience and facilitate the integration of multiple knowledge fields.

As is detailed in (Dos Santos et al., 2023), defining an integrative project with different knowledge areas involved presents a challenge. The problem definition, the assessment, the contents, and other curriculum elements are expected to be aligned properly. A unified effort of the pedagogical team is required to obtain optimal results.

This document presents an experience implementing PBL alongside the Integrative project strategy. The courses of Instrumentation and Measurements, Communication Systems, Communication Networks, and Control Systems were integrated in a Project Based Learning framework for an Electronics Engineering Program with the Control Systems as the leading course. Over two consecutive academic periods (2024-I, 2024-II) activities aimed to integrate these knowledge fields were proposed and performed with students. Curriculum elements were defined and resources presented in (Ramírez-Scarpetta et al., 2024) were used to support the learning experience. At the end of each academic period, students feedback was gathered to assess the relevance of the approach and its alignment with key project design elements in a curriculum.

The rest of this document is structured as follows: details about interdisciplinary courses are presented in section 2, elements of Project Based Learning including resources and materials are discussed in section 3, students' opinions and first assessment of the schema are presented in section 4, discussion and results are presented in section 5, and section 6 concludes the document.

2 Disciplinary Courses

Control Systems, Communications Networks, and Instrumentation and Measurements are courses taken by Electronic Engineering students at the University of Valle during their seventh semester in the program. While each course has its own specific objectives, they collectively support the development of an additional course called Engineering Project II. In this course, various activities including practical training are proposed to guide students through the development of a project that integrates knowledge from all these areas.

The study of control systems is divided into two courses, the first is taken in the sixth semester and the second in the seventh. Similarly, Communication courses span two consecutive semesters beginning in the sixth. In addition, students take Engineering Project I in the sixth semester, which aims to integrate the content from both the Control Systems and Communication courses

Figure 1 shows the connection of the courses of Communications, Control Systems, Engineering Project, and Measurements and Instrumentation for the Electronics Engineering program.

Figure 1. Communication, Control Systems, Engineering Project, and Measurements and Instrumentation courses connections.

The structure shown in Figure 1 enables interdisciplinary problems to be addressed as projects in an engineering context, supporting the development of transversal skills and reinforcing the knowledge in the related disciplines.

2.1 Communication Courses

Communication Systems and Communication Networks are two of three courses in the Communications field in the Electronic Engineering program at the University of Valle. These courses focus on various topics, including but not limited to physical transmission mediums, the OSI model, network applications, and the Internet.

Internet of Things applications (IoT) rely heavily on communication technologies (Behnke & Austad, 2024). Networked control systems applications also depend on robust communication to function effectively (Wang et al., 2024). Different factors such as transmission delays can significantly impact the performance of a controlled system. To integrate the fields of communications and control systems, students are expected to explore various characteristics of the communication infrastructure including reliability through hands-on activities.

The study of communications is supported by learning resources including simulations, animations, analysis tools, and physical devices. Hands-on activities are performed in class and practicing activities are proposed as training. Practical activities of the courses focus on programming and operating network devices such as routers and communication modules. Local area networks (LANs), both wired and wireless, are configured using physical devices where different protocols such as TCP and DHCP are applied to run network applications. Additionally, short-range point-to-point radiofrequency networks are explored through practical exercises.

2.2 Control Systems Courses

In Control Systems courses, students are expected to: define a problem or application; model a system in both continuous and discrete domains as well as input-output and state space representations; analyse the system in time and frequency domains using tools such as root locus and frequency response; define an appropriate expected performance for the system in closed loop operation; and design and implement controllers including a Proportional Integral Derivative (PID), RST, and state feedback (Ogata, 2001).

With the introduction of digital tools and digitally managed equipment such as data acquisition devices, being able to handle and process digital data has become an essential skill for students to develop. Data-driven techniques, such as those used for modelling, are introduced in the courses. Training in data preprocessing and cleaning, aimed at estimating numerical models of a system, is provided to students, particularly concerning modelling discrete representations.

Various learning resources are used to introduce concepts and bridge theory with practice in Control Systems courses. Computational notebooks in MatLab® (MatLab® Live Scripts) are used in class. MatLab® Live Scripts allows running code and embedding text and multimedia elements which students find engaging. Simulations, analysis, calculations, and more, can be included in these computational notebooks. Virtual laboratories are used for hands-on practice. Virtual laboratories enable students to experience the expected behaviour of a real control system in a simulated or emulated environment. Robust laboratory equipment; for example, a continuous current motor-based system, a tank level control system, a pressure control system, and portable prototypes, is used for practical training and project activities. Data acquisition devices, which are also learning resources available for students, connected to a computer allow them to measure systems' variables and use the measured variables to evaluate a compensation signal. MatLab® SimuLink offers libraries to work with different acquisition devices such as the National Instruments MyDAQ®. MatLab® SimuLink and portable data acquisition devices, together, allow the creation of a practical environment for deploying control systems where any type of controller can be implemented digitally.

To integrate knowledge from Communication Systems and Instrumentation, the control system elements, including the controller, the actuator, the process, and the sensor, rely on additional equipment such as communication devices and instrumentation modules. Communication devices are used to connect control system elements located in different places. In (Ramírez-Scarpetta et al., 2024) applications connected to the Internet are presented. Communication modules are also employed to isolate some of the control system elements; for example, the controller and the actuator are connected using radiofrequency modules and they use the air instead of electrical wires as the transmission medium. The previous example enables applications

of IOT as discussed in (Ramírez-Scarpetta et al., 2024). Instrumentation is used with sensors to condition the output signal of the process ensuring it is suitable for the controller.

2.3 Measurements and Instrumentation

Measurement is a process of gathering information from physical variables while instrumentation is the use of measuring instruments to monitor and control processes.

The purpose of this course is to provide students with the basic tools for the conception and design of electronic measuring instruments based on given metrological and electrical specifications, taking into account the various physical, electrical, electronic, adaptation, and signal conversion aspects involved in an electronic measurement chain. To achieve this purpose, the student is expected to be able to: analyze the transduction mechanisms that can be used to sense a magnitude, select the best transducer in terms of what is to be measured and the measurement conditions, design the analog/mixed electronic system that improves the electrical signals delivered by the transducer considering the hardware restrictions, digitize the analog signals without losing relevant information, obtain digital readings in engineering units by applying filtering, linearization, compensation and resolution increase processes, and validate to guarantee the metrological specifications required in a particular solution.

For hands-on activities, students design, simulate, and build signal conditioners for different types of sensors. Students are expected to have experience working on both analog and digital devices, such as operational amplifiers and microcontrollers. Low-cost devices such as the Arduino platform, which is equipped with an analog to digital converter, are proposed for use. Additional available resources to support practical activities for the course include signal generators, power supplies, and multimeters.

3 Project Based Learning and the Engineering Project Courses

((Kolmos et al., 2009)) presented seven elements which must be aligned in a Project Based Learning curriculum design. These elements are: objectives and knowledge, types of problems and projects, progression and size, student learning, academic staff and facilitation, space and organization, and assessment and evaluation. Achieving alignment among these elements presents a significant challenge, particularly when multiple knowledge areas are involved. In such cases each element must be aligned individually including sub elements of those considered knowledge fields.

Each course within the framework does not implement Project-Based Learning independently; instead, PBL is integrated through the Engineering project courses. The activities in individual courses primarily consist of lectures and practical exercises, which do not directly promote active learning. The objectives of each course aim to build foundational knowledge in a specific area while also introducing students to applications related to the other disciplines.

The Engineering Project courses are highly focused on project development. Topics related to project design are introduced and developed within these courses. Lectures and materials provided for the courses aim to equip students with: projects management abilities including time-management, project conception, project execution, and so on; practical experience using the equipment from different disciplines and available learning resources to implement the project solution; financial analysis theory and tools; and practical knowledge of the integrated areas. Projects are divided into stages, each with different objectives. The first stage of the first course focuses on initiation and planning activities with conceptual and basic engineering. The second stage of the second course focuses on detailed engineering.

The context of the problems proposed to students is a control system application. Students work in teams to develop the project. Throughout the project, students are expected to develop transversal skills such as oral and written communication, teamwork, critical thinking, creativity, problems-solving, and others. By the end of the project, students implement the solution of the problem using the available equipment. For the first course, students are expected to use short range wireless modules to connect the controller and the actuator, and deploy a PID controlled system. In the second course, electronic instrumentation modules are used to create the measurement sensor of the control system, local area network devices are proposed to connect the control system elements, advanced controller algorithms, such as RST and state feedback, are desired to be deployed.

The academic staff of the framework is supported by six facilitators (teachers). Each Communications and Control Systems course has assigned one facilitator, with a total of two per area. The Measurements and Instrumentation area has a separate facilitator, while the two Engineering Project courses are supported by an assistant. Each semester, the facilitators of the disciplinary courses assist in the development of the Engineering Project courses, working alongside the assistant. The assistant is responsible for supporting practical activities, which involve training students to use the experimental equipment they will need for their projects.

The courses assess students through reports on the performed training activities, reports on the developed activities for each phase or stage of the project, and presentations of the progress at each stage. Training activities reports correspond to computational notebooks that include the results of the different experiments proposed to be carried out. Data of the simulations, calculations, and so on, generated in experiments is expected to be embedded in the notebooks. Training activities are performed on laboratory equipment. Each phase or stage of the project involves multiple training activities to be carried out before the deadline. Stage reports consist of written documents detailing the results and discussion of the activities proposed. Presentations are lecture-like speeches given by each team member to their peers and the teacher.

4 Students Opinions

The instrument to collect students' opinions was adapted from the quantitative analysis presented in (Alsmadi et al., 2024). In (Alsmadi et al., 2024), the Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (IMMS) (Keller, 2010) was employed to assess the motivational impacts of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) within a multidisciplinary framework. The statements used in the survey, listed in Table 1, were derived from the Motivation Survey. These statements are rated on a scale from 1 to 5 where 1 indicates strong disagreement and 5 indicates strong agreement.

Table 1. Questions of the survey.

ID	Question
Confidence	
Q1	After the initial phase, I felt more confident because I knew what I was going to do in the projects
Q2	The content of the disciplinary and project courses was easier to learn than I initially expected
Q3	For each phase of the projects, the deliverables were consistent with the expected scope of development
Q4	After working on the projects for a while, I felt confident I could pass the planned evaluations
Q5	After completing the project work, I felt confident I could apply it in my professional life
Attention	
Q6	From the initial phase, I became interested in the development of the projects
Q7	The projects were sufficiently practical and realistic, which helped sustain my interest in them
Q8	The way the projects were structured contributed to maintaining my engagement throughout their

	development
Q9	Learning activities such as readings, lectures, hands-on training, exercises, games, and animations supported my sustained interest in the projects
Q10	The project-based courses were engaging and enjoyable
Satisfaction	
Q11	Completing the tasks required by the projects gave me a sense of satisfaction with the achievement attained
Q12	I believe I acquired meaningful learning from both the disciplinary and projects courses
Q13	I genuinely enjoyed working on the projects
Q14	The feedback, evaluation, and comments received throughout the development of the project activities made me feel satisfied with the effort I invested
Q15	I enjoyed working on the projects so much that I look forward to engaging in similar projects in my professional career
Relevance	
Q16	From the initial phase of the projects, I was able to recognize the importance of working on projects
Q17	It is clear to me how the project developments are connected to topics I was already familiar with
Q18	The cases addressed within the projects were of significant relevance
Q19	I learned to perform more effectively within my team as a result of the situations encountered during the project work
Q20	What I learned through the project work will be highly valuable for my professional life

The survey was created using Google Forms and administered to students in class. A total of 9 students participated, all of whom had completed the sixth and seventh semesters and were currently enrolled in the eighth semester of the program at the time the survey was conducted. Demographic information, including ethnicity, age, and gender, was collected to record the respondents' characteristics. Ethnicity categories were based on the classification provided by the National Statistics Administrative Department (DANE) (DANE, n.d.) of the Republic of Colombia. Table 2 presents the demographic composition of the respondents.

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of the students.

Parameter	Genre		Age			Ethnicity		
	M	F	21	22	23	Colombian - African	Mixed	Unrecognized
Value	8	1	5	2	2	1	2	6

Figure 2 summarizes the survey results. The "Q" labels in the figure correspond to the questions listed in Table 1. The gray bars represent the average scores for each question. The red dashed lines indicate the overall average values for each level: 4.1 for confidence, 4.0 for attention, 4.2 for satisfaction, and 4.4 for relevance.

Figure 2. Summary of responses results.

5 Discussion

Most of the responses to each question show consistent variability, generally tending toward values higher than 3. This is considered an acceptable outcome given that this is the first assessment. Questions Q1 and Q12 received notably lower ratings. Question Q1 relates to the early stages of project development, where students are introduced to the project's scope and objectives, and are expected to gain confidence in carrying out the activities. Question Q12 assesses the level of satisfaction after reviewing the knowledge content from disciplinary and project courses. These lower ratings appear as outliers in figure 2 suggesting they are not entirely aligned with the overall response trends.

Questions Q6, Q10, Q13, and Q15 show higher variability. Similar to Q1, Q6 focuses on the initial phase of the projects but emphasizes the attention level. How confident and interested students feel at the beginning; these aspects should be highlighted for improvement in future courses. Questions Q1 and Q8 recorded the lowest average values. Q8 evaluates students' engagement throughout the project development, which may vary depending on the structure of the courses.

In terms of relevance, the results show a high median, with most responses above 4. This is an indicator that the framework could be engaging for students. Q17 received the lowest average score in the relevance level. This question concerns the type of problems and projects presented to students and whether they align with familiar topics covered in the program.

These results help identify specific elements of the framework that may require further attention. However, definitive conclusions cannot yet be drawn, as this is the initial assessment. Additionally, instrument validation is premature at this stage due to the small sample size of only nine responses. Further review is expected as more data becomes available.

6 Conclusion

This paper describes the experience of implementing a PBL and integrative project framework within an engineering program. The experience spans two academic periods, during which the Communications, Control Systems, and Instrumentation and Measurements courses were integrated and aligned to support the development of a new course called the Engineering Project, where the PBL and integrative project framework was deployed. The framework was mainly guided to the Control Systems courses. The implementation of this integrative project strategy, alongside Project-Based Learning (PBL), has been presented as a comprehensive framework for developing both technical and transversal skills in an Electronics Engineering program, and to integrate multiple knowledge areas.

An initial assessment of student acceptance was conducted through a survey, which evaluated four key dimensions: confidence, attention, satisfaction, and relevance. The results emphasize the meaningful impact this framework could have on students' engagement. Future evaluations will be conducted to draw more definitive conclusions about the framework's effectiveness and to refine the assessment tools.

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